

Research

Using Bitcoin as a Payment Method in E-Commerce

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Abstract: The concept of E-commerce has emerged in the last decades of the 20th century as a consequence of the rapidly expanding communication sector. The flourishing and significant growth of E-commerce has led to increasing demand for alternative payment methods of cryptocurrency. In 2009, Bitcoin was introduced as a decentralized digital currency and is now considered as the first virtual currency and the most popular across the global network. This study investigates the feasibility of using Bitcoin for E-commerce payments and implements time series forecasting models to determine its short-term growth. Results show a slow yet steady increment of Bitcoin usage for E-commerce payments, although traditional payment methods will retain its major segment of the market for the next few years.

Keywords: E-commerce; Digital Currency; Cryptocurrency; Bitcoin; Digital Payment.

Introduction

Trade is the voluntary exchange of goods, services, or of both. It is a very old human activity and has considerably contributed to the development of human civilization.

In modern times, trade or commerce prospered remarkably due to developments in technology, transportation, and communication, thereby facilitating the flow and exchange of goods between countries. The emergence of the Internet gave rise to methods of exchange that differ from traditional trade.

Internet technology has not only changed the way we communicate with one another, but has also allowed the emergence of new platforms and online transactions that can radically change the nature of how we carry out the exchange of goods and services. Thus, the concept of electronic commerce (E-commerce) has arisen.

The essence of E-commerce is the sale and purchase of goods and services through electronic channels such as the Internet (web markets).

Online correspondence services enable potential buyers and sellers to communicate and arrange exchanges outside the Internet, while improved encryption methods allow direct trading of bank account details and facilitate payments. The increasing number of web users leads to the emergence of websites and services that rely entirely on paying online advertising revenue.

The rise of Internet-based companies has further expanded E-commerce activities. Specialized online stores have grown to reach a wider market and become leading e-commerce specialists, such as Amazon and eBay. At the same time, innovations in payment platforms have reduced the role of currency, even on physical commerce.

The growth of E-commerce leads to the need for more flexible and convenient electronic currencies for online payments. During the past few years, various cryptocurrencies have emerged and are innovated, and their users increase day by day. At present, Bitcoin currency is the most prominent and is selected for analysis in this study. In 2008, a programmer Satoshi Nakamoto introduced a peer-to-peer digital cash design known as Bitcoin (Ammousa, 2018).

Over time, Bitcoin has attracted increasing attention of economic research. In this study, we investigate the possibility of using digital currencies, Bitcoin in particular, as a payment method in E-commerce. Moreover, we forecast the movement of Bitcoin payment transactions in E-commerce in the next two years, 2021–2022, by analyzing payments transaction volume and price data for the past 10 years from January 2009 to December 2019. The forecast can provide an indication of the future and feasibility of using digital currencies in E-commerce payments globally.

Literature review

1. What is Bitcoin?

Bitcoin is a digital currency that is first introduced in January 2009, following the ideas set out in a whitepaper by the mysterious and pseudonymous developer Satoshi Nakamoto (Ammousa, 2018). Bitcoins are not issued or sponsored by any banks or governments, nor are individual bitcoins valuable as a commodity (FRANKENFIELD, 2019). Reuben Grinberg defines bitcoin as a digital, decentralized, partially anonymous currency, not backed by any government or other legal entity, and not redeemable for gold or other commodity. Bitcoin relies on peer-to-peer networking and cryptography to maintain its integrity (Grinberg, 2012).

Bitcoin is introduced as no more than a vague piece of code (LUTHER, 2016). As the first cryptocurrency, Bitcoin is a decentralized form of digital cash that eliminates the need for traditional intermediaries such as banks and governments to carry out financial transactions (Voigt, 2019). “What is needed is an electronic payment system based on cryptographic proof instead of trust, allowing any two willing parties to transact directly with each other without the need for a trusted third party,” wrote Satoshi Nakamoto in his white paper to first introduce the open-source technology (Voigt, 2019). Bitcoin is increasingly attracting public attention and motivates customers to move towards using this payment system in various businesses. “Fast”, “convenient”, “tax-free”, and “revolutionary” are the terms commonly used to describe Bitcoin (MOHAMED RAHOUTI, 2018). Bitcoins are highly liquid, have low transaction costs, can be used to send payments quickly across the Internet, and can be used to make micropayments (Grinberg, 2012). William J. Luther believes that for those interested in switching to a cryptocurrency, Bitcoin is the obvious choice. As the most familiar cryptocurrency, Bitcoin enjoys relatively lower switching

costs and has the biggest network (LUTHER, 2016). Bitcoin is the world's prime cryptocurrency in view of a market cap. Unlike fiat currency, Bitcoin is created, distributed, traded, and stored by means of a decentralized ledger system known as a blockchain. Bitcoin has a turbulent record as a store of value; the cryptocurrency hit the roof of roughly \$20,000 per coin in 2017, but after two years, its trading dropped for less than half this amount. As the earliest cryptocurrency to meet widespread popularity and success, Bitcoin has inspired a host of offshoots and imitators (FRANKENFIELD, 2019).

In comparison with standard fiat currencies, such as United States (US) dollars or the Euro, a distinctive feature of bitcoins is that the quantity of units in circulation is not subjected to the control of a person, group, company, central authority, or government, but by an accepted and secure software algorithm. A fixed amount of bitcoins is provided at a constant publicly known rate and a priori defined, according to which the stock of Bitcoin increases at a slowing rate. By 2140, the growth rate of Bitcoin is expected to descend to zero, when the maximum amount of bitcoins in circulation reaches 21 million units, assuming that the current algorithm does not change after 2140 (Pavel Ciaian, 2016).

2. Is bitcoin money or commodity?

In general, currency or money is simply defined to have three main functions: a unit of account, medium of exchange, and a store of value (Mankiw, 2007). David Yermak believes that bitcoins fail to fulfill those functions[9], whereas Peter K. Hazletta and other scholars argue that bitcoins are worth the label of money (Peter K. Hazletta, 2019).

Bitcoin is not a physical coin that can be kept in a purse or wallet; rather, it is a virtual currency, a digital computer code stored in a virtual wallet in the network and can be accessed using a computer or smartphone app. As such, bitcoin classification, whether it is money or assets, sparks controversy. According to Nakamoto (2008), Bitcoin is a peer-to-peer electronic cash system that allows online payments to be sent directly from one party to another without the need of an intermediary, such as a bank or any financial institution. This definition indicates that bitcoins are primarily used as an alternative currency. However, bitcoins can also be used as an asset, and thus serve a different purpose. While a currency can be described as a medium of exchange, a unit of account, and a store of value, an asset generally does not possess the first two attributes and thus can be clearly distinguished (Dirk G. Baur, 2018). Gina Pieters argues that Bitcoin is a homogeneous, virtual good that is completely identical across all online markets (Gina Pieters, 2017). On the other hand, Bitcoin volatility has been quite high, sustaining the view that it is a new type of tradable speculative asset, which can work as an imperfect substitute for traditional currencies (Helder Sebastião, 2019).

A certain cryptocurrency identity crisis lies in the fact that Bitcoin was originally conceived as a method of payment, but now rarely bears the hallmarks of a dollar, euro, or pound sterling. In addition, an analytical study by Yelowitz and Wilson using data from Google Trends indicates that the specific concentration of Bitcoin users belongs to the four following categories: computer programming enthusiasts, speculative investors, libertarians, and criminals (Aaron Yelowitz, 2015).

The US Treasury does not define Bitcoin as a currency but as a financial service business. Meanwhile, the Canadian Revenue Agency views Bitcoin as a commodity, meaning that its transactions are considered barter, which generates commercial income.

On October 22, 2015, the European Court of Justice in the European Union (EU) ruled that buying and selling digital currencies is tantamount to a supply of services, and that this is exempt from

value added tax in all member countries. In Finland, Bitcoin is considered as a commodity and not as a currency (BAJPAI, 2019).

3. How to obtain bitcoin?

Essentially, bitcoins (in BTC) can be procured in three ways:

(1) "mining"; (2) purchasing; or (3) by selling items and accepting payments in bitcoin (Turpin, 2014). Mining is the act of creating valid Bitcoin blocks, which requires demonstrating proof of work, and miners are devices that mine or people who own those devices (Wanda Presthus, 2017). Bitcoins can be acquired in a stream of commerce (by exchanging goods and services for bitcoins) or as a reward for participating in "mining," the activity by which users update the network "blockchain," or record of previous Bitcoin transactions. Bitcoins paid out as mining fees represent the seignior age of new currency, which occurs at a fixed rate that periodically declines until its scheduled asymptotic approach to no new money creation in 2140 (Max Raskin, 2016).

The simplest method to obtain bitcoins is to purchase by means of an exchange. Despite its many forms, the underlying concept of exchange is simple: users can trade traditional currency (e.g., dollars, Euros) for BTC at the current exchange rate, which are determined by supply and demand. Users may then store their bitcoins in a wallet file on their personal computer or on the exchange servers, giving them the ability to access their bitcoins from any computer (Turpin, 2014).

4. Legitimacy and legal status

One interesting feature of the fast-growing cryptocurrency market is the flexibility and fluidity of the terms used to describe the different products that fall within its range. A few of the terms used to reference cryptocurrency by country include: digital currency (Argentina, Thailand, and Australia), virtual commodity (Canada, China, Taiwan), crypto-token (Germany), payment token (Switzerland), cyber currency (Italy and Lebanon), electronic currency (Colombia and Lebanon), and virtual asset (Honduras and Mexico) (Rehana Parveen, 2019).

The peer-to-peer digital currency Bitcoin first appeared in 2009 as trade entered a new era of cryptocurrency. While tax authorities, enforcement agencies, and regulators around the world still discuss its best practices, one continuing related question remains: Is Bitcoin legal or illegal? The answer is dependent on user location and activity (BAJPAI, 2019).

At present, Bitcoin operates in a legal grey area. As a new technology, very few laws specifically address virtual currencies. Consequently, an analysis of the legal nature of Bitcoin must consider whether any existing regulations can be applied to this new phenomenon. Such analysis is naturally speculative, and how judges might ultimately rule cannot be known for sure. Nonetheless, gaining a general understanding of the legal environment in which Bitcoin must be considered remains possible (Turpin, 2014)[16]. The EU has not issued any official decision on Bitcoin legality, acceptance, or regulation. In the absence of central guidance, individual EU countries have developed their own Bitcoin perspective. The United Kingdom (UK) has a pro-Bitcoin stance and wishes the regulatory environment to be supportive of the digital currency. There, Bitcoin is subject to certain tax regulations (BAJPAI, 2019).

In China, dealing in bitcoins is illegal. The Chinese government has banned banks and payment institutions from such transactions, warning that BTC is not a currency and should not be circulated or used as such. Wary of potential money laundering risks, the Chinese government has further strengthened the oversight of websites involved with Bitcoin (Turpin, 2014).

Bitcoin is not regulated in Russia, though its use as payment for goods or services is illegal. In Vietnam, the government and its state bank maintain that Bitcoin is not a legitimate payment method. Bolivia, Columbia, and Ecuador have similar stances and ban Bitcoin and other cryptocurrencies (BAJPAI, 2019).

Methodology

In this section, the Time Series Forecasting method is used to predict the future of Bitcoin in E-commerce. Forecasting is the main reason for carrying out time series analysis, with the fundamental idea of using past observations to predict the future. Data selection is first carried out, followed by forecasting. We use two types of Time Series Forecasting methods, namely, Holt Winter's exponential smoothing model and Time Series Forecasting — Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) models.

Time series modeling is a critical research area that has gained research attention over the last few decades. The main objective is to carefully collect the past observations of a time series to develop an appropriate model that describes the inherent series structure. The model is then used to generate future values, or forecasts, for the series. Time series forecasting can thus be termed as an act of predicting the future by understanding the past (T. Raicharoen, 2003). Due to the indispensable importance of time series forecasting in numerous practical fields such as business, economics, finance, science, and engineering (Zhang, 2007), (Zhang, G. Peter, 2003), (Tong, 1983), proper care is necessary to fit an adequate model to the underlying time series. A successful time series forecasting clearly depends on appropriate model fitting. Researchers worldwide have exerted much effort over the years to develop efficient models to improve the forecasting accuracy. As a result, several important time series forecasting models have evolved in literature.

This study selects the monthly data for Bitcoin payments and prices starting from January 2015 until December 2019. The data are collected from [tps://transaction-fee.info](https://transaction-fee.info).

The model that best describes the data is later used to predict the future based on past records. Given that a forecasting model is a functional representation that describes a time series, we forecast the future payments on this basis. Holt Winter's exponential smoothing algorithm is adopted to predict Bitcoin payments for the next two years. In addition, ARIMA models are implemented to predict prices.

Holt Winter exponential smoothing model

Exponential smoothing method was first proposed in the late 1950s as another technique that can be applied to time series data for the purpose of forecasting. While past observations are equally weighted in the simple MA, exponential smoothing uses exponentially decreasing weights over time. The more recent the observation, the higher the associated weight. For the observational sequence $\{x_t\}$ beginning at time $t = 0$, the simplest form of the exponential smoothing algorithm is obtained as:

$$S_0 = X_0$$

$$S_1 = \alpha X_1 + (1-\alpha)S_{t-1}, \quad t > 0 \quad (1)$$

where $\{s_t\}$ is an estimation of the next value of x , α is the smoothing factor, and $0 < \alpha < 1$. Triple

exponential smoothing (suggested in 1960 by Holt's student, Peter Winters) considers both seasonal changes and trends. As mentioned in the previous section, seasonality is a pattern in time series data that repeats itself every L period. Seasonality has two types, namely, multiplicative and additive in nature. For time series data $\{x_t\}$, beginning at time $t = 0$ with a cycle of seasonal change of length L, triple exponential smoothing is given by the following formulas:

$$F_{t+m}(S_t + mb_t)C_{t-1+1+(m-1)mod L}$$

$$S_0=X_0,$$

$$S_t = \alpha \frac{x_t}{c_{t-L}} + (1-\alpha)(S_{t-1} + b_{t-1}),$$

$$b_t = \beta(S_t - S_{t-1}) + (1 - \beta)b_{t-1},$$

$$C_t = \gamma \frac{x_t}{S_t} + (1 - \gamma)C_{t-L}, \quad (2)$$

where F_{t+m} is an estimate of the value of x at time $t + m$ ($m > 0$), α is the data smoothing factor, β is the trend smoothing factor, γ is the seasonal change smoothing factor, $0 < \alpha, \beta, \gamma < 1$, $\{s_t\}$ represents the smoothed value of the constant part (level) for time t , $\{b_t\}$ is the estimation of the linear trend for period t , and $\{c_t\}$ represents the sequence of seasonal factors.

A time series forecasting method is used to conduct the collected predicted dataset of the historical data. The dataset used is from (Bitcoin Protocol Layer Statistics, <https://transactionfee.info/charts/payments-per-day/>) that extends from January 2009 to December 2019. Figure (1) shows the overall data. Clearly, the dataset loses its seasonality due the long time period, making it difficult to predict upcoming data for the next period. Therefore, we used a dataset of the last two years to predict the price values for upcoming data until December 2021, and a dataset of January 2015 to December 2019 to predict the payment values for the upcoming two years. Table (1) lists that actual and predicted datasets.

Table (1): Actual and Predicted dataset

Date	Actual (True) Data		Predicted Data	
	Sum of Payment	Sum of Price	Sum of Payment	Sum of Price
Q1-2015	19151483.00	22579.60	25310636.24	8695686.93
Q2-2015	21618913.00	21535.70	28032720.99	9241395.86
Q3-2015	38274412.00	23424.20	28197045.01	10180465.69
Q4-2015	28582586.00	31749.30	30308408.98	14105565.42
Q1-2016	34417242.00	37312.80	29430175.49	14880831.23
Q2-2016	36873886.00	46494.70	33241565.64	19742569.02
Q3-2016	33128699.00	56555.70	34390062.50	20645664.44
Q4-2016	37887282.00	67158.00	35391599.73	23727820.98
Q1-2017	40546238.00	92924.40	34926897.88	23756223.64
Q2-2017	44200150.00	173630.60	38799892.93	27805328.60
Q3-2017	39052896.00	321414.40	40120483.23	27216290.60
Q4-2017	52580019.00	865122.00	41141496.73	26305096.18
Q1-2018	39158893.00	944711.40	41551245.47	28843806.62

Q2-2018	33237167.00	706041.60	44641218.34	21615900.92
Q3-2018	35453020.00	625925.60	44318575.68	18091548.66
Q4-2018	38302935.00	479859.20	44579251.65	23462608.68
Q1-2019	43084005.00	338792.40	43255724.57	23418830.97
Q2-2019	57047280.00	662757.60	46561433.95	29979115.03
Q3-2019	51023469.00	954436.20	48378486.43	33957426.26
Q4-2019	45211322.00	698291.30	49764476.91	35601775.76
Q1-2020			48610227.22	26651380.84
Q2-2020			51934235.38	28707014.55
Q3-2020			52725374.55	29491249.53
Q4-2020			53851842.76	34654042.82
Q1-2021			53143226.99	34129191.92
Q2-2021			56467235.15	36765057.35
Q3-2021			57258374.31	37772989.36
Q4-2021			58384842.53	44389790.00

Figure (1): Dataset of Bitcoin payments from January 2009 to December 2019

Forecast Metrics

1. Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE)

$$MAPE = \frac{100}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \left| \frac{y_t - \hat{y}_t}{y_t} \right| \quad (3)$$

Properties. This metric:

- 1) Measures the percentage of average absolute error that occurs when forecasting
- 2) Is independent of the scale of measurement (e.g., Min–Max Scaling) but affected by data transformation (e.g., Log Scaling)
- 3) Does not penalize extreme forecast errors
- 4) Provides a measure that is independent from the values observed in the series

5) Is ineffective in data sets where the original measures contain zeros (MAPE $\rightarrow \infty$)*

6) Is easily interpretable by people with no statistical background

*Note: This issue can be avoided by using the modified formula of Symmetric MAPE (SMAPE); however, the performance metric might still diverge if the forecast and the real values are both 0.

$$MAPE = \frac{100}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{2|\hat{y}_t - y_t|}{|y_t| + |\hat{y}_t|} \quad (4)$$

2. R² Score

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (y_t - \hat{y}_t)^2}{\sum_{t=1}^N (y_t - \bar{y}_t)^2} \quad (5)$$

Properties. This metric:

1) Is sensitive to extreme values (outliers).

2) Is used to assess the goodness of fit in a regression model compared with a baseline approach; if R² = 0, then the performance is equivalent to the baseline approach (here, the mean value); if R² > 0, then the performance is better than the baseline and if R² < 0, then the performance is worse than the baseline

3) Cannot indicate if a regression model provides an adequate fit to the data (a good model can have a low R² score while a biased model can have a high R² score, which can be observed mostly in Long Time Series with a huge horizon to forecast)

4) Provides a measure that is independent of the values observed in the series (useful for comparing the performance of a model on different data sets with different scales/range of values)

$$Safe\ Zone = \max \left(\left| 1 - \frac{y_i}{\hat{y}_i} \right| \right) \quad (6)$$

The formula above is used to define the *safe zone* that includes the maximum values for both actual and predicted data.

Time series Forecasting — ARIMA models

ARIMA is a class of statistical models used to analyze and forecast time series data.

This model explicitly caters to a suite of standard structures in time series data, and as such provides a simple yet powerful method for generating skillful time series forecasts.

ARIMA is a generalization of the simpler AutoRegressive Moving Average (ARMA) and adds the notion of integration.

This acronym is descriptive, capturing the key aspects of the model itself. Briefly, they are:

AR: Autoregression - a model that uses the dependent relationship between an observation and a number of lagged observations;

I: Integrated - use of differencing of raw observations (e.g., subtracting an observation from another at the previous time step) to make the time series stationary;

MA: Moving Average - a model that uses the dependency between an observation and a residual error from a moving average model applied to lagged observations.

Each of these components is explicitly specified as a parameter in the model. A standard notation is used of ARIMA(p,d,q) where the parameters are substituted with integer values to quickly indicate the specific model being used.

The parameters of the ARIMA model are defined as follows:

p: the number of lag observations included in the model, also called the lag order;

d: the number of times that the raw observations are differenced, also called the degree of differencing;

q: the size of the moving average window, also called the order of moving average.

A linear regression model is constructed, including the specified number and type of terms, and the data is prepared by using a degree of differencing to make it stationary, that is, to remove trends and seasonal structures that negatively affect the regression model.

A value of 0 can be used for a parameter, which indicates to not use that element. Thus, the ARIMA model can be configured to perform the function of an ARMA model, and even a simple AR, I, or MA model.

Adopting this model for a time series assumes that an underlying ARIMA process generates the observations. This case may seem obvious, but helps to motivate the need to confirm the assumptions of the model in the raw observations and in the residual errors of forecasts.

Model Implementation

This section the describes implementation of both previously proposed models to predict Bitcoin payments and prices.

Table (2): Statistics of payment forecasting model

R ²	MAPE	RMSE	Sig.
50.6 %	14.7	6918359.251	0.076

Figure (2): Payment true data compared with predicted data within a safe range

Table (2) shows the statistics of the time series forecasting of the payment dataset. As shown, the R2 value is 50.6%, which is good for such data. RMSE value indicates how much a dependent series varies from its model-predicted level, expressed in the same units as the dependent series. MAPE shows how much a dependent series varies from its model-predicted level. Independent of the units used, MAPE can therefore compare series with different units. The last indicator is the statistical significance (Sig.), which is the probability that the actual statistic (here, the difference in means) is found if the null hypothesis is true; small p-values ($p \leq 0.05$) tell us that the probability of our actual statistic is low, whereas large values ($p \geq 0.05$) indicate that the probability of our actual statistic is high. Thus, we do not have evidence to reject the null hypothesis, for we obtain a large value that indicates logical forecasting. Figure (4.2) presents a comparison between the true data and the predicted values within a safe range of $\pm 36\%$. Figure (4.3) shows both auto-correlation function (ACF) and partial autocorrelation function (PACF) of the lack of correlation of forecasted data, which suggest its validity.

Figure (3): Payment model residual showing both ACF and PACF

Table (3): Statistics of price forecasting model

R ²	MAPE	RMSE	Sig.
86.4 %	6.28	708526.90	0.070

Figure (4): Price true data compared with predicted data within a safe range

Table (3) shows the statistics of the time series forecasting of the price dataset. As shown, the R² value is 86.4%, which is good for such data. RMSE value indicates how much a dependent series

varies from its model-predicted level, expressed in the same units as the dependent series. MAPE shows how much a dependent series varies from its model-predicted level, and the large Sig. value indicates that the forecasting model is good. The results are independent of the units used and can, therefore, be used to compare series with different units. Figure (4) presents a comparison between the true data and the predicted values within a safe range of $\pm 29\%$.

Results

Depending on the aforementioned statistics and forecasting result, a set of interpretations can be drawn as follows:

1) The predicted results indicate an increase in Bitcoin usage for payment transactions in E-commerce scope for upcoming years.

2) Theoretically, Bitcoin is capable in performing monetary functions and can be used as a payment method in E-commerce; nevertheless, its utilization is still confined within limited scopes.

3) Despite the observed increment of Bitcoin usage, its substitution of traditional currencies is highly unlikely, at least in the coming short-term period.

4) Digital currencies, especially Bitcoin, are increasingly accepted as a payment method around the world.

5) The lack of laws governing Bitcoin has a negative impact on the user trust.

6) Uncertainty and risk involvement negatively affects the rate of Bitcoin usage.

7) The high volatility of bitcoin prices makes it more suitable for speculation than for payments.

8) Bitcoin price volatility makes it unsuitable for term transactions and loans.

1. Can Bitcoin be used as a payment means for E-commerce?

Theoretically, Bitcoin can work as a payment method for E-commerce, and is already accepted in several companies and stores. However, the question is: How far can bitcoin work as a payment method?

This issue is related to a host of challenges and obstacles limiting Bitcoin to serve as a secure and universally accepted payment method, which ordinary users seek. Thus, Bitcoin cannot be a global payment method without legality in all parts of the world. At present, many countries are unreceptive toward Bitcoin and prohibit its use.

Bitcoin can be traded at any time and exchanged for major currencies at low-cost transaction rates (Cagli, 2018)^[20].

The efficiency of using Bitcoin as a payment method varies according to the state's attitude on its usage. For instance, in the US, Bitcoin can be used as payment for goods and services in several companies, small stores, and food shops. By contrast, Bitcoin cannot be used officially in China. Thus, usage is related to the legal position of Bitcoin in each country.

In addition to the legitimacy challenges, security concerns arise regarding the network and the fluctuation of Bitcoin prices and bubbles. Globally, several economists and financial traders show a positive interest in Bitcoin, while others show different levels of uncertainty about the emerging digital currency. However, many retailers and financial companies still show interest in the cryptocurrency, indicating the potential of Bitcoin as an invention worthy of attention.

The growing market capitalization of cryptocurrencies provides the impression of their future significant role in the payment processes in global E-commerce in the coming years, but with unevenness from one country to another.

Conclusions and future outlooks

E-commerce has achieved prodigious advancement in the past 20 years, and is expected to grow further as a common consequence of global evolution in the telecommunications sector. Companies that have adopted E-commerce technologies have the advantage to reach new markets and expand their customer base. Furthermore, E-commerce has a significant impact on single individuals and societies, particularly in expanding different options and alternatives for goods and services and allowing for price competitiveness. E-commerce also opened the way for new job opportunities.

Over the past five years, Bitcoin usage rates have increased in E-commerce payments. This usage is even expected to grow further in the coming years. However, the positive and negative effects that Bitcoin exerts on E-commerce lead to the conclusion that this currency will not reach a larger global expansion in the market and will remain confined to few or limited user range.

Bitcoin may be considered as a worthy alternative to real money, but still lacks adequate maturity and security to gain the trust and acceptance of many users. However, speculators and those who use it as a store of value rather than a medium of exchange find Bitcoin appealing. Several customers who resist Bitcoin as an alternative payment seek digital currency that is subjected to security levels and regulations from higher authority, such as governments. Thus, new digital currencies that are controlled institutions are likely to emerge in the future.

Future research can explore the effect of digital currencies in a specific range, considering that its level of usage vary according to its legal classification in each country. In addition, the potential impact of digital currencies on central banks is similarly of analytical interest.

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